

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING HR MANAGEMENT IN IMPROVING MANAGEMENT IN ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

This article is about the strategic and operational management of activities aimed at increasing the efficiency of the use of human resources in the personnel management system, the use of priorities of HR management, the principles of modern personnel management, continuous and rapid changes in technology, continuous training and development of human resources. information on the results of a number of problematic studies is presented.

Key words

human resources, strategic and operational management, HR management, "Mechnikov's assembler" principle, "stick motivation", "carrot motivation", "personnel costs", "enterprise activity results".

Currently, personnel management is widespread, its task is not only to force and control employees, but also to motivate them, encourage a sense of responsibility and initiative. It is necessary to use new mechanisms of formation of loyalty to the organization, to go beyond the provision of an acceptable minimum wage. Such a mechanism is the personnel management system in the organization. The personnel management system means strategic and operational management of activities aimed at increasing the efficiency of the use of human resources of the organization. In the personnel management system, the main focus is on the organization's need for manpower.

The priorities of HR management are determined primarily by the results of the analysis of existing and planned work. In the personnel management system in the organization, there is a direction of management to individual work with employees. The priority is to improve the efficiency of long-term investments in human capital, rather than seeking to save costs associated with reproducing the workforce. The technology of personnel management system ensures continuous professional growth of employees and improvement of working conditions.

HR management is characterized by the following features:

Modern personnel management is based on the following principles:

1. Systematicity (employee management in the organization:

It should cover the entire composition of employees, not specific categories of employees;

- should solve not one-time tasks, but problems that constantly arise in the employee's activity: from his recruitment, promotion during the period and until the last day of work in the organization;

- not a random decision under the influence of mood, but the use of various methods, tools, methods of working with employees.

2. The consent of the employees of the organization by the Democrats;

- participatory management, that is, the involvement of ordinary employees in the process of managing the organization through participation in quality circles, public bureaus of economic analysis, etc.;

- increase employee awareness of results and prospects.

3. Individualization (implemented in individual planning of professional and workplace growth of employees;

- an individual approach to encouraging the work of performers;

- personal selection of employees taking into account the abilities and individual characteristics of the person).

4. Informatization (includes the use of modern computer technologies for the procedures of collecting, transmitting, processing, storing and issuing information in order to make informed decisions about personnel).

5. Goal orientation.

6. Delegation (consists of transferring part of the powers, rights and obligations assigned to him by the leader to his authorized employees).

7. The principle of "Mechnikov's assembler" ("any management decision must be supported by documents, including, if necessary, financial documents, or materially").

Intangible motivation is a term that speaks for itself - means and methods of motivating employees to achieve goals without the use of money: in organizational, moral and psychological forms of motivation (incentives, verbal incentives) or indirectly material form (presentation of vouchers, meals, payment of VHI policy, etc.). Experienced managers know that an increase in salary does not always lead to a proportional increase in productivity. In addition, it is not always possible to increase the salary fund. Therefore, the skill of non-material motivation of employees is one of the main tools of the manager.

Its competent use makes it possible to: save wages, increase department performance, increase employee loyalty due to more professional management and full employee performance; the manager will gain an understanding of when "stick motivation" works best and when "carrot motivation" works best.

Continuous and rapid changes in technology require continuous training and development of human resources. Organizations with a modern system of internal personnel training are leaders in the competitive environment. It is more profitable and more economical for the organization to improve the efficiency of existing employees based on continuous training than to attract new employees. The main means of developing personnel capacity is training in the enterprise. For this purpose, the management of the company should develop and use the Corporate Education System.

The principles of corporate training are as follows:

- loyalty of employees to corporate culture, values, traditions;
- compliance with business needs, enterprise development strategy;
- continuity of training of employees during the entire working life;
- effectiveness of training, that is, compliance of the results of employee training with the requirements determined by current and future production tasks;
- flexibility, mobility of educational programs, forms and tools, variability depending on the development of educational technologies and educational goals;
- full use of the entire load of teaching tools and methods based on the economic and methodological expediency of their use;
- the unity and compatibility of the theoretical content of educational programs with the actual tasks of students' practice;

- social orientation of educational programs;
- prioritization of the interests of organizations in the process of making decisions on incoming requests for training of different categories of employees.

In modern market conditions, the managers of enterprises and commercial structures of our country must master the appropriate management methods and procedures. These include strategic management, which ensures that enterprises effectively achieve long-term goals based on maintaining competitive advantages and responding appropriately to changes in the external environment. The human resource management function can have a significant impact on enterprise results if the various aspects of human resource management are integrated into a single set of actions, a program that is part of a business strategy.

Thus, strategic enterprise management includes strategy development in the field of personnel management. Strategic personnel management means the management of the formation of the organization's competitive labor potential, the management that allows the organization to develop and achieve its goals in the long-term perspective, taking into account the current and future changes in the external and internal environment. The effectiveness of the personnel policy of the enterprise in the implementation of the main directions of personnel work (formation, use and development of the labor potential of the organization) is determined by the implementation of the personnel control function aimed at planning, management, control and management support.

The ultimate goal of supervision is regular, objective and comprehensive assessment of employee performance. This assessment is primarily aimed at optimizing management decisions in the field of personnel policy and ensuring the competitiveness of the company's strategy in the field of personnel.

Currently, many foreign companies and some of our country's companies, which traditionally worked in the production sector, have started to switch to service provision. However, labor costs are higher than capital costs in many industries.

That is, there are companies that can be classified as "intensive" or "employee-dependent" businesses. In addition, there are areas such as industry, in which the reliability of employees determines the reliability of equipment and the operation of the entire company in general. And the reliability and efficiency of its operation may depend on how effectively the funds allocated to the company's employees are used. Thus, the development of modern business leads to the need to organize effective management of personnel costs and, accordingly, to make changes to the traditional personnel management system. These changes are primarily related to

the introduction of control in the field of personnel management. Personnel control is aimed at accounting and monitoring of personnel costs, as well as optimization of these costs.

The generalization of the experience of domestic and foreign companies allows to form the main goal of the company's modern personnel management system: to provide the necessary quantity and quality of personnel for the company, to organize its effective use, and to optimize the total costs of employees, along with professional and social development.

In accordance with this goal, in addition to the traditional subsystems, a personnel management system is being formed: subsystems of planning, forecasting and personnel marketing; subsystems for registration and accounting of employees; includes the labor relations subsystem, etc., the personnel cost management subsystem.

The main functions of this subsystem are:

- employee cost planning,
- organizing their use,
- control and analysis of cost effectiveness.

Such development of the personnel management system requires changing one of the main elements of this system - the company's personnel management service. It is necessary to establish a financial responsibility center for personnel expenses on the basis of personnel management service.

THIS ALLOWS:

1. Provide a systematic approach to personnel management in the enterprise.
2. Ensuring operational risk management in the field of personnel management.
3. Planning, controlling and analyzing the use of expenses for the implementation of personnel policy, as well as direct management of factors that prevent the implementation of plans in this area.
4. Ensuring high efficiency in making management decisions in the field of personnel management when the internal or external environment of the enterprise changes.
5. Provide optimization of personnel costs through operational control and the ability to analyze these costs.
6. To ensure that the head of the personnel service makes decisions on the redistribution of financial resources aimed at the formation, use and development of the personnel potential of the enterprise, which increases the effectiveness of its actions when the internal or external environment of the enterprise changes.

7. Ensuring the full use of employee control functions, evaluating the effectiveness of the HR service in general in terms of "personnel costs" - "enterprise activity results".

In conclusion, we think that it would be appropriate if the following directions of personnel management were defined and applied in the activity for a large industrial company.

Ways to develop the use of HR management in the enterprise.

We believe that the implementation of the necessary personnel changes and reorganization of its work, the involvement of an external consultant for the purposes are important in the development of HR in the enterprise.

Thus, if the above recommendations are implemented in the activities of industrial enterprises, an industrial enterprise with strong, qualified management and qualified personnel, as well as favorable opportunities in the external environment, will take all necessary steps to prevent and neutralize threats from the external environment, and to get rid of weaknesses in personnel management. We believe that it will have the basis and conditions.

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